

“Aligning Technology Architectures with Cross-Domain Metadata Models” - Dagstuhl Workshop, October 6-11, 2024: Summary Report

Overview

The DDI Alliance and CODATA sponsored a workshop titled “[Aligning Technology Architectures with Cross-Domain Metadata Models](#)” held at Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz Center for Informatics in Wadern, Germany from October 6 to October 11, 2024. The main focus of the workshop was on the DDI-CDI specification, which is now going through the approval process at the DDI Alliance for its 1.0 release. Main topics focused on tools development and support for the specification, and future

work within the group. This included some initial discussions with the W3C liaison regarding prospects for collaboration.

The event was attended by 24 experts, including members of the DDI-CDI Working Group and the Qualitative Subgroup, members of the broader DDI community, and invited experts from the Dataverse community and relevant W3C committees. The work was organized around topical subgroups, which are described below. Overall, the event was a major success – each of the groups was able to meet their goals in terms of substantive outputs, and plans for further work established.

Further information can be found on the [workshop wiki](#).

Syntax Representation

This group continued the on-going work on the generation of syntax representations and supporting tools from the model. The highest priority outputs were to define ShEx and SHACL expressions to enable validation of the RDF syntax representation of the DDI-CDI model. A secondary priority was to generate a JSON Schema for the JSON-LD syntax representation specifically. The RDF representations are seen as very useful for DDI-CDI, as many of the domains from which data needs to be described in DDI-CDI use RDF rather than XML as their primary approach when encoding metadata.

All of these outputs were realized by the end of the workshop, and testing can now begin. Although not part of the DDI-CDI 1.0 specification, these supporting artefacts are expected to make the specification easier to implement, and to support adoption, particularly in the FAIR community.

W3C Liaison

In years past, the DDI Scientific Board has established a simple liaison with W3C – Darren Bell, co-chair of the SB, is the primary contact. Pierre-Antoine Champin is the W3C representative. Both were in attendance at the workshop. The goal of the group was two-fold: to explore what parts of the DDI product suite might be usefully promoted to W3C as recommendations, and to formulate a plan for carrying them forward.

Good progress was realized in both areas. Substantively, the variable cascade – present in both DDI-CDI and DDI Lifecycle – provides a means of bridging the physical encoding of data with the logical and conceptual. While W3C has many different recommendations for describing data (CSV on the Web, DataCube, and SSN/SOSA for wide, multi-dimensional, and long formats, respectively), none have the richness of DDI in terms of connection to reusable variable structures and links to

formalized concepts. An approach to defining the variable cascade in a useful form for enriching these W3C formats was discussed, and seems to offer a useful enhancement to the current W3C recommendations.

Organizationally, it was proposed that the group for working on this specification could be a joint one, supporting participation not only by the W3C membership, but also by those active in the DDI community. This would require that a formal agreement be put in place between the W3C and the DDI Alliance, similar to that which W3C has with the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). (OGC was seen as a good model, as they also produce their own specifications, many of which are also ISO standards, and some of which are jointly developed with W3C. Thus, they would seem to offer a useful example to follow).

Exploration in both areas will be further explored by a group of volunteers from among the participants, coordinated through the DDI Alliance Scientific Board. Potential core candidates for such a joint working group were identified – the full membership being determined once the group is officially formed, from among the W3C and DDI communities.

Tools Development

The group working on tools development had a range of potential outputs. Primary to this was the identification of the features to be implemented in the Dataverse platform for supporting DDI-CDI. In addition, a functional description of the requirements for DDI-CDI support in the Nectar tool being developed by the DDI Developer's Group was prioritized. Further, a tool for generating the Croissant ML format for documenting data sets to be used as training data for LLMs was identified as a desirable output, with the possibility of tools for generating DDI-CDI metadata from various input formats.

An agreed set of features for Dataverse support was identified, and an initial draft of a paper explaining the purpose and intention written. The work in the Dataverse platform is funded by a grant at IQSS, so implementation will be taking place in the near term. Key development staff from IQSS at Harvard attended the workshop. The business case for this support was the product of both Harvard and Dataverse Community members (the chair of the community group was also in attendance.) This document is seen not only as good for communicating plans to the Dataverse community, but also as a more general example of DDI-CDI implementation. It builds on the existing features within Dataverse for DDI Codebook, and also on the Data Explorer metadata editing capabilities developed at Scholar's Portal in Canada.

A set of requirements for input to the upcoming DDI Developer's Group Hackathon were also written, and these will serve a double purpose for describing editorial capabilities which could be added to the Dataverse Data Explorer application.

A script for producing Croissant ML from DDI-CDI was developed during the course of the workshop, as well as an AI-driven tool for documenting data in DDI-CDI. These tools are in early form, and will require some further development and testing against more complete examples.

Qualitative Support in DDI-CDI

The Qualitative Subgroup of DDI-CDI met at the workshop, picking up on work started at a Dagstuhl workshop in 2023, and carried forward within the DDI Alliance over the course of the intervening year. The goal of this work is to permit the description of qualitative and mixed-media data in addition to and in combination with traditional quantitative data.

The outcome of the workshop was significant: a proposal for how such data can be described within the frame of the existing DDI-CDI model was substantially developed. Further work at a face-to-face meeting in the margins of the upcoming EDDI conference in Chur is planned. This represents a major step forward for this group, although integration of the proposal into the DDI-CDI model will require further work.

Summary

Although the goals of the workshop were diverse, excellent progress was made in each area of focus. The intention is not only to provide support for DDI-CDI, although that was a major thread, but also to integrate DDI-CDI with other DDI products at a practical level. This goal was achieved, with Dataverse and the progress in exploring a connection with W3C providing the clearest examples. Collaboration with the DDI Developer's Group is also desirable, and it is hoped that the upcoming Hackathon (and further developments around the Nectar tool) will prove fruitful. The workshop also promised to further support uptake of DDI-CDI within the FAIR community, especially by providing support for the RDF implementations typical there.

Scientific Work Plan 2024 – 2026 Goal		Topic Group
3.7	Support development of RDF serialisations for DDI products that do not currently have them.	Syntax Representation
1.3	Deepen connection with W3C and explore the possibilities of a W3C recommendation for DDI components, such as the variable cascade.	W3C Liaison
1.4	Broaden scope and opportunities for DDI tools development by promoting the work of the DDI Developers WG and engaging third parties.	Tools Development
3.8	Support development and release of new products and versions of products in the DDI Product Suite.	Qualitative Support in DDI-CDI

Alignment between goals of the DDI Alliance [Scientific Work Plan 2024 – 2026](#) and the topics addressed at the workshop